

SUICIDE PREVENTION RESOURCES AND INFORMATION

Warning Signs

From the **National Institute of Mental Health** (For more visit: bit.ly/485hanp)

- Talking about:
 - wanting to die, being a burden to others, great guilt or shame.
- Changing behaviors such as:
 - Making a plan or researching ways to die.
 - Withdrawing from friends, saying goodbye, giving away important items, or making a will.
 - Displaying extreme mood swings.
 - Eating or sleeping more or less.
 - Using drugs or alcohol more often.
 - Taking dangerous risks such as driving extremely fast.
- Feeling:
 - Empty, hopeless, trapped, or having no reason to live.
 - Extremely sad, more anxious, agitated, or full of rage.
 - Unbearable emotional or physical pain.

Firearm Safety & Storage

- Safely storing firearms is crucial for preventing the risks of suicide, unintentional death, or injury. For detailed information, tips, and pictures about firearm safety, locks, and storage options from the **Utah Department of Public Safety** visit: bit.ly/3EljS8r. Or scan the following QR code:
- **Lock to Live** is an online tool that helps people make decisions about temporarily reducing access to potentially dangerous things, like firearms, when they feel hopeless, down, alone, or suicidal. Visit lock2live.org or scan the following QR code:

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Resources

- For resources on suicide data, ideas for prevention, infographics, and other information visit the **Suicide Prevention Resource Center's** online library: bit.ly/401pQtg
- The **9-8-8 Suicide & Crisis Lifeline** is available 24/7 to offer free and confidential support. Call or text 9-8-8 or go to 988lifeline.org to chat with someone online.
- For finding specific mental health therapists (e.g., therapists by race/ethnicity):
 - Visit **Psychology Today** (psychologytoday.com), and find a therapist by race/ethnicity in your state by clicking on "Find a Therapist" and enter your state, then click "all filters". You can filter by race/ethnicity, diagnosis, age, gender, language, and type of therapy.
 - Visit mentalhealthmatch.com and enter your information to be matched with a therapist.
- **The American Foundation for Suicide Prevention** (<https://afsp.org/suicide-prevention-resources/>)
- **American Association of Suicidology**
- **How to Talk to a Child about a Suicide Attempt in Your Family** (MIRECC)
- **Man Therapy**
- **Mental Health America**
- **National Action Alliance for Suicide Prevention**
- **Now Matters Now**
- **The Dougy Center** – The National Center for Grieving Children and Families
- **The Jason Foundation**
- **The Jed Foundation**
- **Parents, Families, Friends, and Allies United with LGBTQ People** (PFLAG)
- **SAVE**
- **The Society for the Prevention of Teen Suicide**
- **StopBullying.gov**
- **The Trevor Project**
- **The Tyler Clementi Foundation**
- **Veterans Crisis Line**
- **Wounded Warrior Project**

References

(References for "Circumstances Leading Up to Firearm Suicide Among Hispanic/Latino Adults: Understanding the Challenges and How We Can Help")

1. Conner A, Azrael D, Miller M. Suicide case-fatality rates in the United States, 2007 to 2014 a nationwide population-based study. *Ann Intern Med.* 2019; 885-895.
2. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. Fatal injury data. Web-based Injury Statistics Query and Reporting System (WISQARS), National Center for Injury Prevention and Control. Available at <https://wisqars.cdc.gov/>.
3. *Hispanic Firearm Suicide Decedents: Identifying Circumstances and Typologies with National Violent Death Reporting System Data (R21MD019447)*. Information available at: <https://reporter.nih.gov/search/RA0bRDeAa0qhs6fsVpid9A/project-details/11193977>.

